

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for PPP2R5D for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and immunohistochemistry

Riham Ayoubi¹, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Chunling Chen², Kathleen Southern¹, Stefan Strack², Vincent Francis¹, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

² Department of Neuroscience and Pharmacology, University of Iowa, Iowa City, United States

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

PPP2R5D is the delta (δ) isoform of the serine/threonine-protein phosphatase 2A. Abundantly expressed in the brain and involved in a broad range of cellular processes, PPP2R5D plays an essential role in modulating key neuronal pathways and signalling. Pathogenic mutations in the *PPP2R5D* gene are linked to clinical symptoms characterized by neurodevelopmental delay, intellectual disability, and autism spectrum disorders. The etiology of these genetic disorders remains unknown, which can partly be due to the lack of independently characterized antibodies. Here we have characterized five PPP2R5D commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

Q14738, *PPP2R5D*, PPP2R5D, Serine/threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit delta isoform, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence, immunohistochemistry

Introduction

Protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A) is a ubiquitously expressed serine/threonine phosphatase that regulates various cellular functions including cell metabolism, cell cycle, DNA replication, transcription and translation, signal transduction, cell mobility and apoptosis (1-4). The PP2A-B56 family of the regulatory subunit has 5 isoforms: α , β , γ , δ , and ϵ . The *PPP2R5D* gene encodes serine/threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit delta (δ) isoform (PPP2R5D) (5, 6). This δ isoform is highly expressed in neuronal tissues and is crucial for cell cycle regulation. It controls the ability of PP2A to negatively regulate PI3K/AKT signalling pathways and modulates GSK3 β and cyclin-dependent kinase 5 activities by controlling tau phosphorylation (7, 8). Missense mutations in *PPP2R5D* have been linked to neurodevelopmental disorders such as neurodevelopmental delay (9), intellectual disability (10-12) and autism spectrum disorder (13-17). The majority of these mutations lead to Jordan's syndrome, an autosomal dominant illness associated with intellectual disabilities and autism spectrum disorders (17).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols and openly sharing the data (18). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (18). Here we characterized a total of five commercial PPP2R5D antibodies selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of PPP2R5D properties and function. The five antibodies were screened for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and immunohistochemistry.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (19) and in Table 3 of this data note (18).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (20, 21). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than 2.5 log₂ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (22). The HAP1 expresses the *PPP2R5D* transcript at 5.7 log₂ TPM+1, and a *PPP2R5D* KO HAP1 cell line was obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1).

First, the five PPP2R5D antibodies were tested by western blot using HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO protein lysates. Samples were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and probed in parallel (Figure 1A). Based on manufacturer predictions for cross-reactivity with the mouse ortholog, two recombinant antibodies were then selected for western blotting on brain homogenates from WT and *PPP2R5D* KO mice (Figure 1B). The reported molecular weight of PPP2R5D detected by western blot varies across internal antibody manufacturer data and the published literature. To explore whether buffer conditions influence the apparent molecular weight, we compared denaturing and non-denaturing lysis protocols. Using HAP1 wild-type and *PPP2R5D* knockout lysates prepared in either RIPA (denaturing) or IP (native) buffer, we found that PPP2R5D predominantly migrates at ~64 kDa with RIPA buffer and ~74 kDa with IP buffer (Figure 1C).

We then assessed the capability of these five antibodies to capture PPP2R5D from HAP1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, the PPP2R5D antibody, ab188323**, identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, the five antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the PPP2R5D antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (18).

The five antibodies were then tested in immunohistochemistry. First, FFPE sections from WT and *PPP2R5D* KO HAP1 cell pellets were used (Figure 4). The two mouse-reative antibodies confirmed by western blot (refer to Figure 1B) that only stained WT HAP1 were then evaluated for chromogenic signal in brain, lung and muscle tissues from WT and *PPP2R5D* KO mice (Figure 5).

In conclusion, we have screened five PPP2R5D commercial antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and immunohistochemistry by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cells and mouse tissues from WT and *PPP2R5D* KO. To assist users in interpreting antibody performanyce, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all four applications (22). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect PPP2R5D were identified in all applications.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available PPP2R5D antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. Moreover, the same antibody clones are donated by 2-3 manufacturers (cross-licensed antibodies), effectively serving as replicates and enabling the validation of test reproducibility. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on [Protocols.io](https://protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization) (protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization) (18). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (23, 24).

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Peroxidase-conjugated VeriBlot for IP detection reagent is from Abcam, cat. number ab131366. Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). OmniMap anti-Rabbit HRP is from Roche Diagnostics (VENTANA, cat no. 760-4311).

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in LaemmLi loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/mL}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Mouse brain homogenization

Mouse brains from WT and *PPP2R5D* KO were lysed with 10 strokes of a homogenizer in HEPES buffer (10mM HEPES, pH 7.4) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix. Lysates were centrifuged at 2500x *g* for 5 min at 4°C and post-nuclear supernatants were collected. Supernatants were incubated for 30 min at 4°C with Triton X-100 added at 1% final concentration. Supernatants were spun at ~110,000x *g* for 30 min at 4°C. Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels as described above.

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µL of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µL of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 mL aliquots at 2 mg/mL of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 mL of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. VeriBlot for IP Detection Reagent:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.1 µg/mL.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary *PPP2R5D* antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/mL for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with

395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (25). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Antibody screening by immunohistochemistry

HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cells were washed and fixed for 30 mins in 10% Neutral Buffered Formalin (MilliporeSigma, cat. number HT501320). Cells were washed and embedded in histogel (Fisher Scientific, cat. number HG4000012) at a ratio of 1:1. WT and *PPP2R5D* KO mouse tissues were fixed for 48 h in 10% formalin. HAP1 cell pellets and murine tissues were processed using the Tissue-TEK VIP, then paraffin embedded using the Leica EG1150 tissue embedding center. A tissue microarray (TMA) composed of 2 mm cores of each cell pellet and mouse tissue was prepared using a TMA grand master. 2 µm sections were placed on charged slides and stained using the BenchMark ULTRA from Roche Diagnostics, cat. number 05342716001. Antigen retrieval was performed at 95°C for 65 mins using the ULTRA Cell Conditioning 1 Tris-based buffer at pH 8.0-8.5 (VENTANA, cat. number 950-500). The substrate DAB from the DISCOVERY ChromoMap DAB Kit (VENTANA, cat. number 760-159) was applied for 8 mins and Hematoxylin (VENTANA, cat no. 760-2021) was used as a counterstain. Bright field images were acquired with an Aperio slide scanner using 20x objective and exported using the NPD view software.

Data availability*Underlying data*

Dataset for the PPP2R5D antibody screening study. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10119577.

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

Grant information

The grant was from a Canadian Institutes of Health Research Foundation (grant no. FDN154305) and by the Government of Canada through Genome Canada, Genome Quebec and Ontario Genomics (OGI-210). The study was also funded in part by the Simons Foundation Autism Research Initiative (SFARI).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank -GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

References

1. Tung HY, Alemany S, Cohen P. The protein phosphatases involved in cellular regulation. 2. Purification, subunit structure and properties of protein phosphatases-2A0, 2A1, and 2A2 from rabbit skeletal muscle. *Eur J Biochem.* 1985;148(2):253-63.
2. Alberts AS, Thorburn AM, Shenolikar S, Mumby MC, Feramisco JR. Regulation of cell cycle progression and nuclear affinity of the retinoblastoma protein by protein phosphatases. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 1993;90(2):388-92.
3. Glenn GM, Eckhart W. Mutation of a cysteine residue in polyomavirus middle T antigen abolishes interactions with protein phosphatase 2A, pp60c-src, and phosphatidylinositol-3 kinase, activation of c-fos expression, and cellular transformation. *J Virol.* 1993;67(4):1945-52.
4. Ronne H, Carlberg M, Hu GZ, Nehlin JO. Protein phosphatase 2A in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*: effects on cell growth and bud morphogenesis. *Mol Cell Biol.* 1991;11(10):4876-84.
5. Janssens V, Goris J. Protein phosphatase 2A: a highly regulated family of serine/threonine phosphatases implicated in cell growth and signalling. *Biochem J.* 2001;353(Pt 3):417-39.
6. McCright B, Brothman AR, Virshup DM. Assignment of human protein phosphatase 2A regulatory subunit genes b56alpha, b56beta, b56gamma, b56delta, and b56epsilon (PPP2R5A-PPP2R5E), highly expressed in muscle and brain, to chromosome regions 1q41, 11q12, 3p21, 6p21.1, and 7p11.2 --> p12. *Genomics.* 1996;36(1):168-70.
7. Louis JV, Martens E, Borghgraef P, Lambrecht C, Sents W, Longin S, et al. Mice lacking phosphatase PP2A subunit PR61/B'delta (Ppp2r5d) develop spatially restricted tauopathy by deregulation of CDK5 and GSK3beta. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2011;108(17):6957-62.
8. Shang L, Henderson LB, Cho MT, Petrey DS, Fong CT, Haude KM, et al. De novo missense variants in PPP2R5D are associated with intellectual disability, macrocephaly, hypotonia, and autism. *Neurogenetics.* 2016;17(1):43-9.
9. Biswas D, Cary W, Nolta JA. PPP2R5D-Related Intellectual Disability and Neurodevelopmental Delay: A Review of the Current Understanding of the Genetics and Biochemical Basis of the Disorder. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020;21(4).
10. de Ligt J, Willemsen MH, van Bon BW, Kleefstra T, Yntema HG, Kroes T, et al. Diagnostic exome sequencing in persons with severe intellectual disability. *N Engl J Med.* 2012;367(20):1921-9.
11. Gilissen C, Hehir-Kwa JY, Thung DT, van de Vorst M, van Bon BW, Willemsen MH, et al. Genome sequencing identifies major causes of severe intellectual disability. *Nature.* 2014;511(7509):344-7.
12. Stessman HA, Xiong B, Coe BP, Wang T, Hoekzema K, Fenckova M, et al. Targeted sequencing identifies 91 neurodevelopmental-disorder risk genes with autism and developmental-disability biases. *Nat Genet.* 2017;49(4):515-26.
13. Abrahams BS, Arking DE, Campbell DB, Mefford HC, Morrow EM, Weiss LA, et al. SFARI Gene 2.0: a community-driven knowledgebase for the autism spectrum disorders (ASDs). *Mol Autism.* 2013;4(1):36.
14. Basu SN, Kollu R, Banerjee-Basu S. AutDB: a gene reference resource for autism research. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2009;37(Database issue):D832-6.
15. Iossifov I, O'Roak BJ, Sanders SJ, Ronemus M, Krumm N, Levy D, et al. The contribution of de novo coding mutations to autism spectrum disorder. *Nature.* 2014;515(7526):216-21.
16. Satterstrom FK, Kosmicki JA, Wang J, Breen MS, De Rubeis S, An JY, et al. Large-Scale Exome Sequencing Study Implicates Both Developmental and Functional Changes in the Neurobiology of Autism. *Cell.* 2020;180(3):568-84.e23.
17. Sandal P, Jong CJ, Merrill RA, Song J, Strack S. Protein phosphatase 2A - structure, function and role in neurodevelopmental disorders. *J Cell Sci.* 2021;134(13).
18. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Gonzalez Bolivar S, Alende C, Ruiz Moleon V, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nat Protoc.* 2024.
19. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made F1000Research 2023. 2023;12:1344.
20. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolahdouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife.* 2019;8.

21. Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Shlaifer I, Ayoubi R, Edwards AM, Durcan TM, et al. Identification of highly specific antibodies for Serine/threonine-protein kinase TBK1 for use in immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. *F1000Res.* 2022;11:977.
22. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife.* 2023;12.
23. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023;51(D1):D358-d67.
24. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech.* 2018;29(2):25-38.
25. Stringer C, Wang T, Michaelos M, Pachitariu M. Cellpose: a generalist algorithm for cellular segmentation. *Nat Methods.* 2021;18(1):100-6.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC003155c003	CVCL_TG11	HAP1	<i>PPP2R5D</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the PPP2R5D antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab188323**	1023484-1	AB_3065198	recombinant mono	EPR15617	rabbit	0.239	Wb, IP, IF, IHC-P
Abcam	ab188325**	GR169019-2	AB_3065199	recombinant mono	EPR15617-50	rabbit	0.315	Wb, IP, IF, IHC-P
Cell Signaling Technology	5687*	1	AB_10829041	monoclonal	H5D12	mouse	0.077	Wb, IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-18066*	YE3914232	AB_2539449	monoclonal	H5D12	mouse	1.0	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-26647*	YE3914196	AB_2725096	monoclonal	OTI3B3	mouse	1.0	Wb, IHC-P

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence; IHC-P=immunohistochemistry (paraffin), **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody,

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and immunohistochemistry

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 (22)

Figure 1: PPP2R5D antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 4: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunohistochemistry on HAP1 cells

Figure 5: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunohistochemistry on murine tissue

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: PPP2R5D antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated PPP2R5D antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab188323** at 1/10 000, ab188325** at 1/10 000, 5687* at 1/200; MA5-18066* at 1/200, MA5-26647* at 1/200. Exceptions were given for antibodies 5687*, MA5-18066* and MA5-26647*, which were titrated to the corresponding dilutions found below, as the signals were too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. **B)** WT and *PPP2R5D* KO mouse brain homogenates were prepared, and 60 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated PPP2R5D antibodies. Antibody dilutions used: ab188323** at 1/10 000 and ab188325** at 1/10 000. **C)** Lysates of HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO were prepared in RIPA or IP lysis buffer. ab188325** was used at 1/10 000 for western blot. PPP2R5D is observed primarily at 64 kDa in RIPA buffer and at 74 kDa in IP buffer. Predicted band size: 70 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed overnight using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated PPP2R5D antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the PPP2R5D antibody ab188323** diluted at 1/5000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on clear flat-bottom 96 well. Cells were stained with the indicated PPP2R5D antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/mL, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab188323** at 1/200, ab188325** at 1/300, 5687* at 1/70, MA5-18066* at 1/1000, MA5-26647* at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunohistochemistry on HAP1 cells.

A) HAP1 WT and *PPP2R5D* KO cell pellets were fixed and paraffin embedded. TMA sections of WT and KO cells were mounted onto slides and stained with the indicated PPP2R5D antibodies followed by the corresponding multimer HRP secondary. Chromogen image acquisition was performed, and representative images of each core are shown. All antibodies were diluted at 1/100 as recommended by the supplier. Core images of WT and KO cells captured in the same field of view are shown. **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 5: PPP2R5D antibody screening by immunohistochemistry on murine tissue.

WT and *PPP2R5D* KO tissues from mouse brain, lung and muscle were fixed and paraffin embedded. TMA sections of WT and KO tissues were mounted onto slides and stained with the indicated PPP2R5D antibodies followed by the corresponding multimer HRP secondary. Chromogen image acquisition was performed, and representative images of each core are shown. All antibodies were diluted at 1/100 as recommended by the supplier. Core images of WT and KO tissues captured in the same field of view are shown. **= recombinant antibody.